

Charlotte Wien

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Holding a master's degree in library and information science, and a Ph.D. in information retrieval and having extensive work experience from both the Royal Danish School of Library and Information Science and from the University Library of Southern Denmark. That topped with an extensive network in the relevant European networks and Library associations like LIBER, NWB, SPARC Europe and DFFU and ILIDE.

Currently full professor of Scholarly Communication. Area of research: Bibliometrics including gaming of bibliometric measures. The Open Science movement and the influence of New Public Management on researchers' publication behaviors. Teaching activities within Responsible conduct of research, scientific methodology, and information retrieval.

Employment:

2025-: Professor emerita of Scholarly Communication, Department of Community Medicine, Arctic University, Tromsø. Task: Head of WP5 of the project "Healthy Choices" and supervisor of two PhD-students.

2022 - 2025: Professor of Scholarly Communication, Clinical Department, OPEN (Odense Patient Data Explorative Network). Full tenure track professor. Task: To establish a research unit on Scholarly communication within health sciences. Teaching: Responsible conduct of research to PhD-students.

2023-2025: Vice President of European Library Relations, Elsevier Verlag. Networking for and with research libraries and librarians in Europe. Attending up to 25 conferences for librarians per year presenting and hosting workshops for research librarians. Conveying information about Elsevier's strategy and products to librarians and information about librarians concerns back to Elsevier. The job was not to sell Elsevier's products but to bridge the gap between the scientific publishing industry and the research libraries. (leave from position at SDU)

2016 - 2022: Head of the Department of Research and Analysis, The University Library of Southern Denmark Responsible for the development and daily operations of the library's services to researchers and PhD-students. Services included Research Data Management, Bibliometric reports, Advanced Information Retrieval for Systematic and Scoping Reviews, Plagiarism check of research, research registration (Pure). Courses in Responsible Conduct of Research to both PhD-students and research managers, digital humanity services to researchers, establishment, and daily operations of "The Philotek" (a special facility for PhD-students for presentations and for lectures).

2014-2016: Full Professor and Assistant Dean of research, College of Communication and Media Science, Zayed University, Dubai. Obtaining massive international experience in completely different cultural settings. Field of expertise Media and Communication studies. Teaching scientific methods and media theory

2000 - 2014: Associate Professor at the Faculty of Social Sciences. Including Associate professor at the Journalism Department, at the Political Science Department and at the Marketing & Management department. Area of expertise: Science communication in mass media. Teaching scientific methods. Services to the university: 12 years as head of Study (master's program in journalism) and massive experience with academic curriculum building.

1992 – 2000: Various roles. Included Assistant Professor, Department of Journalism; Teaching Assistant in Centers for Classical Studies, Contemporary Middle East Studies, and later Classification at Royal School of Library and Information Science; PhD student; Research Assistant Centre for Contemporary Middle East Studies.

Education & Training:

2018: "LIBER emerging leaders' program"

2009: Research Manager, Copenhagen Business School

1998: Ph.D. Information Retrieval

1994: Master of Library Science (MLS) (Royal School of Library and Information Science, Denmark)

1992: M.A. in Humanities, University of Southern Denmark

International networks and board memberships:

2023-2025: Participation in more than 45 international conferences and library events in Europe, Africa and the Middle East
2021-2023: Executive board DFFU (The association of Danish Research Libraries)
2019-2025: Executive Board, Syddansk Universitetsforlag/SDU University Press
2019-2023: Executive Board, SPARC Europe – Setting the Default to Open
2018-2023: ILIDE conference program committee
2018-2020: Chair of the LIBER WG on Innovative Metrics

Arranging Conferences and hosting events:

- Countless workshops on GenAI for Librarians (i.e. in Norway, England, Cyprus, Scotland, Denmark, South Africa, and Egypt)
- In my capacity as certified Lego Serious Play instructor: Countless workshops for librarians and researchers using LSP (i.e. in Germany, Italy, Latvia, Poland)
- ILIDE2022: Program Committee member <https://www.ilide.eu/>
- LIBER2022: Responsible for Social Program and overall coordination of the conference <https://liberconference.eu/thank-you-for-attending-liber-2022-in-odense-denmark/>
- 26th Nordic workshop on Bibliometrics and research policy (NWB2021): Floor manager <https://event.sdu.dk/nwb2021>

Teaching, lecturing and presentations:

- Having almost 30 years of university lecturing experience I have extensive teaching experience. My teaching evaluations normally range between 4 and 4.5 on a scale from 0-5 (5 being best).
- My research area (Scholarly communication) has made me a “high in demand” presenter at intern seminars at the scientific departments and various researcher networks.
- Finally, my career as researcher, librarian and Vice President of Library Relations has enabled me to participate in more than 200 conferences over the years presenting posters, participating in panels, conducting workshops, presenting papers and as keynote on several occasions and at both scientific, stakeholders and practitioners conferences

Other Qualifications and Activities:

Honorary offices:

2018-2023 Ambassador for Videnskab.dk (science communicating web magazine)
2018-2020: Member of The Research Ethics Committee (REC), SDU
2012-2017: Adjunct professor at Ilisimatusarfik (University of Greenland)
2009-2013: Member of the advisory group for the
BA in Library science and knowledge communication, SDU
2009-2013: Member of the advisory group for BA-programs at Ilisimatusarfik (University of Greenland)
2007-2013 Member of network for Nordic Journalism programs
1998-2018 External examiner, (Royal School of Library and Information Science, Denmark)
1993-1998: External Subject Specialist, Library of University of Southern Denmark

Selected editorial work:

2008–2012: Member of the editorial board of ‘Journalistica’
2008-2009: Member of the editorial board of ‘Gerontologi’
2007 - present: Member of the editorial advisory board of ‘Journalism & Mass Communication Educator’
1993-1995: Editor of ‘Mellemøst-informations månedsoversigt’
A regular reviewer for several high ranked international journals like Scientometrics.

Leadership experience:

2019-2022: Director of Research at The University Library of Southern Denmark
2017-2022: Head of Researcher Services, at the University Library of Southern Denmark (Functional responsibility for approx., 50 staff)
2016-2022: Head of the Research and Analysis section, The University Library of Southern Denmark (staff responsibility for 15 staff)
2015-2015: Assistant Dean of Research and Graduate Studies/Zayed University
Ph.D-Supervision: Supervised 8 candidates over 20 years

Languages:

Danish: Mother tongue
English: Fluent reading, writing and speaking
Norwegian and Swedish: Fluent reading (the Nordic languages are mutually understandable when speaking)
German and French: Good reading skills, some speaking

Publications:

More than 200 including scientific articles, books and book chapters (a full list can be supplied upon request)

Personal:

Birthdate: January 29th, 1965. Married, one child.

